

Sustainability in Family Controlled MSME - A Bibliometric analysis of factors in India¹

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Abstract

The paper identifies and addresses a significant research gap by identifying factors contributing to the sustainability of family controlled MSMEs in India which is crucial sector for India's growth and GDP.

The paper performed bibliometric analysis to identify key factors that are responsible for sustainability. The bibliometric analysis was performed using 717 papers identified from SCOPUS database covering publications from 2010 to 2025. Co-occurrence analysis, co-citation analysis and thematic clustering were performed to identify research trends and themes in this domain.

Four important and crucial themes were identified for the sustainability of family controlled MSMEs in India. They are Family goals, succession planning, family culture and entrepreneurial orientation.

The findings highlight the need for further qualitative research to validate these identified factors. The paper at the end a comprehensive roadmap, providing critical insights for researchers and practitioners to develop effective sustainability strategies for Indian family-owned MSMEs

Keywords

Family-owned MSMEs, Sustainability, India, Bibliometric Analysis

1. Introduction

Family-owned business (FOB) is the most prominent form of business across the globe. FOB can be understood as the business which is owned or controlled by the family members or other close relations (Chauhan & Garg, 2020). They are defined by the family's extent of control over the business through the mechanisms like ownership stake, board representation or sometimes through management roles. Hence through these ways, families have a significant control over the business (Besim, 2023, Kinger-Hans et al., 2023).

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Family business plays a very crucial role in global economy. Its contribution to the global GDP is well understood and documented and also more importantly, its significant contribution to the global employment cannot be avoided. The contribution to the global GDP from family business ranges from 70 % to 90 % (Luo, 2019; Priya, 2021). Especially in the regions like Latin America and country like China, family business has contributed significantly to their GDP and also to their R&D efforts and budget (Luo, 2019). One factor which contribute to the globalisation efforts of family business is engaging in internationalisation and hence taking full advantage of globalisation to enhance and scaleup their operations (Massis et al., 2018; Fathallah & Carney, 2024; Kewitz et al., 2012). The increased presence of family business in global stage can be attributed to their characteristic of high entrepreneurial spirit, dynamism and innovation. In spite of the challenges, that they face at various levels like getting appropriate management skills and resources, family business has emerged as successful contributor to the global economy (Priya, 2021). Table given below provides a glimpse of the contribution of family-owned businesses to the major global economies.

Figure 1: Visual Capitalist (2024). Family-Owned Businesses by Share of GDP

From the figure above it is clear that family-owned business forms an important contributor to the Indian economy. They contribute to the extent of 79% to the Indian GDP. They are also one of the major contributors to the employment (Takahashi & Srivastava, 2025; Malik, 2018). The first contribution of FOB to the Indian economy comes in the form of economic impact. FOBs in India are one of the major contributors to the employment generation as well (Kota & Singh, 2016). Indian FOBs are the world's third largest hub for family business with 111 public companies having valuation of USD 840 billion (Takahashi & Srivastava, 2025). Indian FOBs are identified to be attached with factors like succession planning, innovation and mentorship which are crucial for sustainability of family businesses in India. These factors in turn helps the Indian FOBs to navigate growth and maintain its competitiveness (Varshney et al., 2024). Ashwin, Krishnan, and George (2015) have identified that family involvement in business positively influences R & D investments particularly in high tech industries like pharmaceuticals, thereby promoting innovation and technological advancements.

There is also another important element to the FOBs in India; which is the small and micro enterprises or Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Indian terms. According to Ministry of Micro, small and medium enterprises, Government of India, Micro enterprises are those who has investment in plant and machinery or equipment of not more than Rs. 2.5 crore and annual turnover not more than Rs. 10

crore, small enterprises are those who has investment in plant and machinery or equipment of not more than Rs. 25 crore and annual turnover not more than Rs. 100 crore and medium enterprises are those who has investment in plant and machinery or equipment of not more than Rs. 125 crore and annual turnover not more than Rs. 500 crores (Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises [MSME], n.d.). MSMEs in India contribute significantly to the economy by having contribution in the area like GDP, employment and exports etc. They are major driver to the growth of Indian economy. Nath (2024) discusses the contribution of MSMEs in Indian economy in the form of employment generation, GDP contribution, export promotion, entrepreneurship development, regional development, innovation, income distribution and support to large industry. MSMEs are also major employment generator to the rural and economically weaker section of society. They contribute to about 30% of the India's GDP. In the area of export, MSMEs contributes to about 45% of total export. They decentralises the economic activity by reducing the urban concentration. They also serve as suppliers and sub contractors to large industries, and maintaining the robust supply chain (Nath, 2024).

There are major portion of family businesses in India that are MSME in nature ("A Diagnostic Analysis of Problems of MSMEs in India", n.d., Jayakumar (2023)). Nurunnabi and Kusz (2021), have identified a major hurdle for Indian family MSMEs is the lack of proper and professional succession planning in place. Their studies claims that only one third of family business MSMEs successfully transit to next generation. Indian family owned MSMEs are "key drivers of innovation" by adopting the changes and thereby fostering the innovation and entrepreneurship. They also act as bridge to urban-rural divide by protecting the migration from rural to urban areas by developing the local employment. Also, they promote economic inclusivity by offering opportunities to marginalised communities which also includes women and people from other backward section of the society.

Though there are numerous literature which has dealt with the area of family controlled/owned business and MSMEs in India. But none of them has talked about the family owned MSMEs in India and the factors responsible for their sustainability. There is lack of focussed research on MSMEs in India from family-owned business perspective (Gupta & Bhattacharya, 2016; Singh, 2013). Hence by considering the importance of family owned MSMEs to India both in terms of providing employment and contribution to GDP / economy, it is important and imperative to lookout the factor which are specifically responsible for their sustainability, so that a clear understanding can be developed and also can be useful for the future researcher aspiring to work in the same area.

Thus, this paper tries to address that gap.

The objective of this paper is:

- i. To perform bibliometric analysis of literatures available in the area of family controlled MSMEs in India.
- ii. To identify the factors (independent variable) responsible for the sustainability (dependent variable) of family controlled MSMEs in India.

2. Background

The term family controlled / owned business has been variedly defined amongst the literature available across the world, but there is not one single accepted definition of the term "family controlled" or "family

owned” business. Definitions have varied on the basis of ownership pattern, influence of family values or sometimes the degree of involvement of family in the business. But if we observe those definitions collectively, we will find that all of them in some or other way talks about importance of significant family ownership, control over the business decisions and more importantly over the generations.

Definition of family-owned business can be understood under family ownership pattern, its control pattern that may span up to future generations and its influence on the business decision.

If we consider the ownership pattern, family-owned business can be considered as that business which has considerable control over the strategic business decision directly or indirectly (Shumbambiri & Mwenje, 2023; Kumar, 2024; Ruíz-Viñals & Álvarez-Gómez, 2018; Davis, 1983; Lau, 2010).

From the management and involvement perspective many authors have understood that family-owned business are those businesses where family members hold a key position in the business and does not only limited to having the ownership in the business (Kumar, 2024; Ruíz-Viñals & Álvarez-Gómez, 2018; Davis, 1983; Lau, 2010).

While some of the authors have considered the importance of family values in the family-owned business regardless of the degree of control of the family over the business. They have also given the importance to interactions between the family and business system and also the dynamics of family values over the business and its functioning (Chua, Chrisman, & Sharma, 1999; Litz, 1995; Davis, 1983).

On the other hand, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises holds an important position in the contribution terms in Indian economy. “The Gross Value Added (GVA) by MSMEs in India’s GDP was 29.7% in 2017-18, rising to 30.1% in both 2022-23. Even amid the unprecedented challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the sector sustained a contribution of 27.3% in 2020-21, rebounding to 29.6% in 2021-22” (Press Information Bureau, 2024). The contribution of MSMEs does not only comes from the GVA to the GDP, it comes in other forms as well like industrial production, exports and more importantly, contribution to the employment in the Indian economy. The definition and understanding of MSMEs in India have evolved over the years, sometimes with investment as base, sometimes turnover and sometimes employment size as base (Lokhande, 2011). Even the latest definition of MSME (as discussed above) is also based primarily on the size of investment and the turnover. There is greater demand from other perspectives also to include other dimensions like employment contribution and sectoral characteristics in the definition of MSMEs to make it more dynamic and inclusive (Shetty & Shetty, 2020). The basic idea here is to align the definition with the international requirement and keeping it par with the latest development across the world. MSME in India is identified as major engine of growth along with other important sector like agriculture, investment and exports.

Importance of MSMEs in Indian context comes in the form of following points:

- i. Contribution in terms of employment: MSMEs in India employs almost 25 crore people (Press Information Bureau, 2025). By providing the employment to these many people, MSME provides the livelihood to millions of Indians.
- ii. Contribution in terms of exports: The contribution in terms of export is highly significant. Out of the total volume of export, more than 45% for the year 2024-25 (till May 2024) of the export value was from the MSME produced products. The value of the exports stood ₹12.39 lakh crore

in 2024-25 (Press Information Bureau, 2025). The number signifies the importance and contribution of MSME in India's global standing in export market.

Thus, MSME are not just a contributor to the Indian economy but also acts as a fundamental part in India's economic structure by contributing in terms of employment generation, addition in GVA, growing participation in export and their foundational role in manufacturing sector.

With all these contributions to the Indian economy in direct / indirect way, the sustainability of MSMEs becomes important for economy and for employment generation as well. Though there are certain factors responsible for sustainability has been identified, a detailed study is highly warranted for. These studies have identified the factors as internal and external factors which includes innovation, management support, financial resources, government initiatives and technological advancement etc. There are additional other factors have also been identified as organisational coordination and training and market focus and branding (Khurana, Haleem, & Mannan, 2019; Mondal, Singh, & Gupta, 2024; Khurana, Haleem, Luthra, & Mannan, 2021; Lahiri & Banerjee, 2019; Khurana, Mannan, & Haleem, 2020; Babber & Mittal, 2023).

Inspite of these factors responsible for sustainability of Indian MSMEs identified and followed up by these organisations, there are challenges too, which is dominant in their cases. The challenges identified are:

- i. Financial challenges like limited access to finance and collateral requirement etc. (Bisht & Singh, 2020).
- ii. Technological challenges like low adoption and limited knowledge of digital skills (Mohan & Ali, 2019).
- iii. Human resources like talent retention, skill gap (Hattiambire & Harkal, 2022).
- iv. Regulatory framework like limited support from government and complex legal structure (Chary & Rao, 2016).

Family controlled MSMEs forms a major portion of Indian industrial scenario. While there are no precise number available for family controlled MSMEs in India, there are certain estimates are available. It is estimated that most of the family-owned businesses in India falls under MSME category. There is trend of multigenerational involvement in the family business is observed, where first and second generation are actively involved in almost 70% of the business. Specifically, 83% of the family manufacturing units falls under MSME category, while 73% of family business under service sector falls under MSME category (SPJIMR, 2023).

Hence, looking at the contribution of this section of Indian industrial scenario in terms of employment generation, GDP, exports etc. it becomes imperative to understand the factors responsible for the sustainability of family controlled MSMEs, since there is considerable gap in research which involves study in the sustainability of family controlled MSMEs. To address this gap, systematically identifying the literatures and hence identifying the factors responsible for sustainability of these enterprises, a systematic literature review along with bibliometric analysis was carried out in this paper. The detailed methodology adopted is detailed in the following section.

3. Methodology

To perform a literature review on the above said area, bibliometric methodology was adopted. Bibliometric analysis can handle large volume of literature data thus providing valuable quantitative insights by providing clear objective and with that we can map the research trend also while in case of SLR, it offers qualitative analysis only (Passas, 2024). Hence with bibliometric analysis we get scalability and efficiency (Pulsiri & Vatananan-Thesenvitz, 2018). It also offers trend analysis and helps in formation of structure mapping (Zupic & Čater, 2014) thus offering a comprehensive coverage (Cheng, Wang, Xie, & Yan, 2023).

To conduct the bibliometric analysis, we followed the steps suggested by Donthu et al. (2021). According to them, bibliometric analysis should have proper data collection from relevant databases like Scopus or Web of Science, which is followed by performance analysis. Once the performance analysis is done, then scientific mapping has to be performed, which is followed by network analysis, clustering and visualisation and at the end interpretation and reporting.

4. Data Collection

For the purpose of data collection, Scopus database was used instead of other data bases like Web of science. Scopus has wider coverage of peer reviewed journal and hence has intense representation of quality research papers from across the discipline which includes paper from almost every country, region and the language (Pattnaik et al., 2021, Valtakoski, 2020).

Data obtained from Scopus are also prone to corrections and error. Once the data was collected, it was cleaned to have specific representation of objective desired. The given below procedure was adopted to reach to a final collection of 717 papers. The table 1 illustrates the procedure to perform the search in Scopus database, as outlined by Goodell et al. (2021)

Table 1: Search criteria and article selection.

	<i>Search criteria</i>	<i>Reject</i>	<i>Accept</i>
a	Search engine: <i>Scopus</i>		
b	Search date: <i>14 April 2025</i>		
c	Search term: <i>KEY ("family business") OR KEY ("family owned business") OR KEY ("family enter?")</i>		3633
d	Subject area: <i>"Business, Management and Accounting", "Social Sciences"</i>	503	3130
e	Document type: <i>"Articles", "Conference papers", and "Book chapter"</i>	181	2949
f	Access: <i>All Open Access</i>	2088	861
g	Year of Publication: <i>2010-2025</i>	14	847
h	Publication Stage: <i>Final</i>	16	831
i	Keywords: <i>Family Business, Family Businesses, Succession, Innovation, Family Firms, Sustainability, Gender, Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Firm Performance, Family Structure, Family Business Succession, Familiness, Decision Making, Family-owned Business, Family</i>	48	783

	<i>Firm, Succession Planning, Family Involvement, Women, Small Family Business, Family Ownership, Family Business Management, Family-owned Businesses, Family, Business Family, Family Entrepreneurship, Family Dynamics, Business Families, Small Family Businesses, Small And Medium-sized Enterprise, Family Control, Family Business Groups.</i>		
j	Language screening: <i>Include documents in English only</i>	40	743
k	Source type: <i>Journal, Conference proceedings, Books</i>	26	717
l	Content screening: <i>Include articles if "Titles, abstracts, and keywords" indicate relevance to scope of study</i>	0	717

As mentioned earlier, Scopus database was used to perform the analysis. The keywords KEY ("family business") OR KEY ("family owned business") OR KEY ("family enter?") was used to get the desired result. In that the subject area was chosen as "Business, Management and Accounting", "Social Sciences", since the subject region in which we propose to work in from these areas. To include maximum papers, document type "Articles", "Conference papers", and "Book chapter" was used. All of them were "All open access" type of document so that it should be easy and approachable for us to go through the papers without any hassle. To have more recent outlook, papers from the year range 2010 to 2025 was used. Further, to get the specific result for the study, following keywords were used: Family Business, Family Businesses, Succession, Innovation, Family Firms, Sustainability, Gender, Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Firm Performance, Family Structure, Family Business Succession, Familiness, Decision Making, Family-owned Business, Family Firm, Succession Planning, Family Involvement, Women, Small Family Business, Family Ownership, Family Business Management, Family-owned Businesses, Family, Business Family, Family Entrepreneurship, Family Dynamics, Business Families, Small Family Businesses, Small And Medium-sized Enterprise, Family Control, Family Business Groups. These keywords include all the dimensions and factors for the study. The language chosen for the papers was English so that maximum paper can be included for the study, since most of the papers written were in English language. For the document type "Articles", "Conference papers", and "Book chapter" was used. The source chosen was Journal, Conference proceedings, Books. To get the article which should be relevant for the study "Titles, abstracts, and keywords" was used at the end.

Thus, at the end after applying all the data cleaning process and others, as mentioned above, a total corpus of 717 papers was found relevant for the study. Once the paper was shortlisted by applying the above detailed filtration, they were added to VOSviewer to have further analysis and detailed study.

5. Findings

5.1 Publication status of relevant papers:

The figure generated by Scopus to understand the number of publication is from the year 2010 to 2025 which is also the range of years for the study.

The publication activity as shown in graph below is very low in the early years, specifically from the year 2010 to the year 2015, perhaps around 5 to 10 documents. There was increase in trend, noticed in the years 2013, 2014 and 2015 with only around 20 papers. This clearly indicates the low, initial phase of scholarly interest in the area identified.

After the year 2015, the graph showed a significant rise in the publication activity, which is clear from the sudden rise of graph in that year. Thereafter the trend in publication was on continuous rise. The number of documents around which was 20 in the year 2016 grew to 40 and then 60 in the year 2018 and 2019 respectively. The most productive years came in and after the year 2020 which had around 80 papers publication. Then came the years 2021 and 2022 which saw the publication of around 95 and 100 papers respectively. The peak reached in the year 2023 with the number was around 110 papers. This increment in the number of papers in recent past clearly indicates the growing interest in the area of family owned MSME research. There is unexpected activity is found for publication in the year 2024 and 2025, where there is sudden fall in the number of papers. In the year 2024 the number of publications was around 20 papers whereas in case of 2025, the number fell to single digit.

The sharp decline in the number of publications in these years may be due to the incomplete data available for these years. For the bibliometric analysis, may be because of the cut off date the number of papers selected was very low. If the incomplete data is not the reason, then unexpected fall in the research area is the matter of concern. However, given the nature of bibliometric studies usually capturing completed publications, this sharp drop for those years is most likely due to the data extraction date (which in our case was 14th April, 2025).

Figure 1: Publication trend

5.2 Top authors, institutions and countries:

Table 2 details about the top authors, institution and countries in terms of publication and citation. Alfredo De Massis emerged as most impactful and influential author with 2567 total citation with 29 total publications. The dual accomplishment of the author clearly indicates the reach and penetration author's work has in the area of family business research. Other authors with impactful work are Josip Kotlar

with 969 citations followed by Allan Discua Cruz with 263 citations. In this aspect Josip Kotlar emerged as more influential with total of 12 publications.

In terms of institution / universities Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy emerged as the university with highest citation 481 which is followed by Zhejiang University, China with 385 citations. But if we look at the total production, Zhejiang University, China emerged as highest in terms of publication with total of 6 publication. Other major contribution comes from Lancaster University Management School, United Kingdom, with multiple entries in the table. This may be because of the publication comes from different keywords. With 368 citation and publication 5, it comes next to Zhejiang University, China.

While going through the country wise contribution United Kingdom emerged as major contributor in terms of citation with 5201 citations. It also tops in terms of total publication, the number of which is 142. Then there is sudden decline in, both production and citation. Next in the table is another European counterpart, which is Italy with total citation of 3685 and total production of 97. It is followed by United States with total citation of 3070 and total publication of 69. Since the focus of our work is India. And if we look the India's standing in the table, it has 445 citations with 19 as total production which is relatively smaller especially when we look into the importance of the concept to the Indian economic scenario.

Table 2: Top authors, institutions, and countries for research in the area of family business / family-owned business.

TC	Author	TP	TC	Institution	TP	TC	Country	TP
2567	De massis, Alfredo	29	481	Free University Of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy	5	5201	United Kingdom	142
969	Kotlar, Josip	12	385	Zhejiang University, China	6	3685	Italy	97
263	Discua cruz, Allan	9	368	Lancaster University Management School, United Kingdom	3	3070	United States	69
247	Mcadam, Maura	9	283	Lancaster University Management School, Lancaster, United Kingdom	5	2725	Canada	43
246	Clinton, Eric	8	235	Free University Of Bozen-Bolzano, Bolzano, Italy	5	2068	Germany	62
549	Dawson, Alexandra	8	224	Lancaster University, United Kingdom	3	1740	Spain	94
292	Basco, Rodrigo	7	113	Dublin City University, Ireland	3	1187	Switzerland	22
1020	Chrisman, James j.	7	102	Free University Of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy	4	988	China	32
194	Kammerlander, Nadine	6	102	Lancaster University Management School, United Kingdom	4	688	Sweden	32

535	Miller, Danny	6	68	Robert Gordon University, United Kingdom	4	621	Australia	23
72	Petrů, Naděžda	6	62	Lancaster University Management School, United Kingdom	3	600	France	32
250	Campopiano, Giovanna	5	52	University Of Wolverhampton, United Kingdom	3	462	Austria	17
110	Cassia, Lucio	5	31	Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland	3	445	India	19
951	Chua, Jess h.	5	29	Imd Business School, Switzerland	3	329	South Africa	29
38	Forés, Beatriz	5	23	Imd Business School, Switzerland	3	288	Portugal	20
341	Nordqvist, Mattias	5	15	University Of The Basque Country, Spain	3	283	Czech Republic	34
21	sanchez- famoso, Valeriano	5	12	The Slovak University Of Agriculture In Nitra, Slovakia	3	212	Poland	27
99	Seaman, Claire	5	8	Nelson Mandela University, South Africa	3	207	Malaysia	18
16	Venter, Elmarie	5	8	University Of Skövde, Sweden	3	75	Mexico	18

TC: Total Citation, TP: Total Production

5.3 Top journals

Top journals for research in the area of family business / family-owned business are given in the table 3. Table 3 depicts the journals which are highly cited along with their total publication in a separate column. In terms of total citation, Journal of Family Business Strategy has the maximum citation with 2606 total citation. This is followed by journal Family Business Review with total citation 1206. Their total publication is 42 and 21 respectively. Looking at the total publication column, Journal of Family Business Management has the maximum number of publications with 47 total publications so far. Sustainability (Switzerland) has the second highest publication with 45. These number reveals that as far as quality of article and journal as a whole is concern, Journal of Family Business Strategy has maximum impact and effectiveness. This is clear from going through the number of citation and total publication. Even though the top two journals have lesser publication but their citations are way ahead then other journals in the list.

It is clear from the table 3 that in the period of years from 2022 to 2025 the production of almost all the journals has increased sparing few. Especially in case of Journal of Family Business Management, it has shown steep rise in the production of 33 in the above said period which is followed by Sustainability (Switzerland) with 22 total productions in the period of year 2022 to 2025.

For the journal which are specifically from the “Family Business” genre, the total production is almost same as that of the journals from other genre. This shows that, though these journals are not specifically meant for the theme “Family Business”, they are publishing the article from the said theme which highlights the importance of theme “Family Business” to the current business scenario.

Table 3: Top journals for research in the area of family business / family-owned business.

Journal	Family Business	TC	TP	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018	2019-2021	2022-2025
<i>Journal of Family Business Strategy</i>	x	2606	42	4	5	7	8	18
<i>Family Business Review</i>	x	1206	21	2	3	5	3	8
<i>Entrepreneurship: Theory And Practice</i>		960	11			2	5	4
<i>Journal of Family Business Management</i>	x	852	47	2	3	1	8	33
<i>Sustainability (Switzerland)</i>		581	45			3	20	22
<i>Journal of Business Research</i>		405	15				5	10
<i>European Journal of Family Business</i>	x	269	46			14	15	17
<i>International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship</i>	x	264	6			1	4	1
<i>International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research</i>		235	12			1	3	8
<i>Entrepreneurship And Regional Development</i>		229	6		1		2	3
<i>Administrative Sciences</i>		148	14			1	5	8
<i>Long Range Planning</i>		93	6			1		5
<i>Cogent Business and Management</i>		82	6			2	2	2
<i>Business History</i>		74	8		2	2	1	3
<i>Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review</i>		68	7			1	2	4
<i>Journal of Risk and Financial Management</i>		34	6				3	3
<i>Journal of Evolutionary Studies in Business</i>		30	8				5	3

<i>Corporate Ownership and Control</i>		22	11	4	6	1		
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5.4 Top Article:

Top cited articles are presented in table 4. The segregation is made on the basis of the total citations made in Scopus. According to this, Zellweger T.M et al. (2012) emerged as most cited and hence most impactful article with total of 653 citations. It is followed by De Massis A. et al. (2014) with total of 438 citations. Another article by same author, De Massis A. et al. (2018) comes next to it with 438 citations.

Zellweger T.M et al. (2012) in their work have taken socio economic view of family-owned business. Their emphasis is on the valuation of business in not on the financial front only. According to them the valuation of firm goes beyond the financial aspect. It has attached an emotional viewpoint to the family business. De Massis A. et al. (2014) work, though was related to the conduction of research in the field of family business, have emphasised that family business is a complex area / domain to study. There is element of emotional attachment in the operations and running of family business. Thus, according to them, looking at the complexity of the nature of family business, to understand the true nature of family business, a proper case study method has to be employed, mere quantitative analysis will not only do the purpose. Whereas in case of De Massis A. et al. (2018), they talk about the growth in terms of internationalisation of family business. According to this paper, the internationalisation effort of the family business depends upon the type of family involvement (ownership v/s management, generational stage etc.), specific situation / dynamics in each of family business individually and at the end the external environment to the family business.

Further analysis of top cited papers revealed impactful and influential work in the area of risk-taking ability and concentration of family wealth so that the power should be retained within the family (Miller D. et al., 2010), innovation (Erdogan I. et al., 2020), value system inside the family business, CSR (Marques, P et al., 2014), innovation in family business (Rondi E. et al., 2019), governance, family business control (Chang S.-J. et al., 2015), gender issues, women involvement (Campopiano G. et al, 2017), governance, succession, family business goals (Chirico F. et al., 2020), family business values, succession, entrepreneurship orientation (Alsos G.A. et al., 2014), family control, family business values (Miroshnychenko I. et al., 2021), family control, entrepreneurship orientation, family values (Fang H. et al., 2018), family succession, succession planning, gender issues, governance (Nelson T. et al, 2017), sustainability, family values, innovation (Broccardo L. et al., 2020), succession in family business (Garcia P.R.J.M. et al., 2019), gender issues, women in family business (Chadwick I.C. et al., 2018).

Table 4: Top Articles

S.No	Name of Author	Title of Paper	Year	Citations
1	Zellweger T.M et al.	Family control and family firm valuation by family CEOs: The importance of intentions for transgenerational control	2012	653

2	De Massis A. et al.	The case study method in family business research: Guidelines for qualitative scholarship	2014	438
3	De Massis A. et al.	Family firms in the global economy: Toward a deeper understanding of internationalization determinants, processes, and outcomes	2018	326
4	Miller D. et al.	Family ownership and acquisition behavior in publicly-traded companies	2010	320
5	Erdogan I. et al.	Managing the Tradition and Innovation Paradox in Family Firms: A Family Imprinting Perspective	2020	252
6	Marques P. et al.	The Heterogeneity of Family Firms in CSR Engagement: The Role of Values	2014	214
7	Rovelli P. et al.	Thirty years of research in family business journals: Status quo and future directions	2022	197
8	Rondi E. et al.	Unlocking innovation potential: A typology of family business innovation postures and the critical role of the family system	2019	169
9	Chang S.-J. et al.	When does transitioning from family to professional management improve firm performance?	2015	160
10	Campopiano G. et al.	Women's involvement in family firms: Progress and challenges for future research	2017	159
11	Chirico F. et al.	To Merge, Sell, or Liquidate? Socioemotional Wealth, Family Control, and the Choice of Business Exit	2020	141
12	Alsos G.A. et al.	Kinship and business: how entrepreneurial households facilitate business growth	2014	140
13	Miroshnychenko I. et al.	Family Business Growth Around the World	2021	135
14	Fang H. et al.	The pursuit of international opportunities in family firms: Generational differences and the role of knowledge-based resources	2018	133
15	Nelson T. et al.	Sex and Gender in Family Business Succession Research: A Review and Forward Agenda From a Social Construction Perspective	2017	132

16	Fletcher D. et al.	Qualitative research practices and family business scholarship: A review and future research agenda	2016	131
17	Broccardo L. et al.	Sustainability as a driver for value creation: A business model analysis of small and medium enterprises in the Italian wine sector	2020	117
18	Garcia P.R.J.M. et al.	Perceived parental behaviors and next-generation engagement in family firms: A social cognitive perspective	2019	117
19	Dawson A. et al.	Advancing Family Business Research Through Narrative Analysis	2012	117
20	Chadwick I.C. et al.	Women leaders and firm performance in family businesses: An examination of financial and nonfinancial outcomes	2018	113

5.5 Co Occurrence analysis

Figure 2 details about the co-occurrence analysis which in turn reveals how frequently terms or keywords appear together within the theme of family business there by indicating the main themes and their relationships. The following figure contains nodes, which are specific term or keyword, node size details the frequency of appearance of keywords. The larger the keywords, the greater number of times the keyword has appeared or are more central to research. There are links (lines) which represent the co-occurrence, which in turn means that the two connected terms have appeared together in the same paper. The thicker the lines are, the greater number of times they have appeared in research together. There are colours also which refers to the clusters. The different colours mean different theme or cluster of co-occurring keywords.

Red cluster in the figure is the largest cluster with “family business” dominance at the centre. It includes the keywords "social emotional wealth", "firm performance", "family managed business", "innovation", "internationalization", "finance", "next generation", "governance", "human capital", "ownership", "dilemma", and "board". This cluster has core research on “family business” with focus on their performance outcomes along with unique aspect like socio economic wealth, governance, succession and financial consideration etc. The stronger connection between “family business” and “firm performance” reveals a major area of research interest.

Green cluster has keywords like “entrepreneurship”, “corporate social responsibility (CSR)”, “business model” and “family enterprises”. This theme explores the entrepreneurial capability of family business and how these family businesses are engaging with CSR. This cluster has inclination towards the aspect that how family business is engaging with innovation, business model and their impact on the society.

Blue cluster has more of research related keywords like "qualitative research", "theory", "literature review", "methodology", and "research". This cluster is more inclined towards this aspect that how

& Ding, 2014). Figure 3, talks about the co citation analysis based on authors. The different colour of nodes (here it is red, green and blue clusters) represents clusters of authors based on their thematic similarity. This reveals groups of authors who have frequently co cited together, because their work relates to similar themes. The size of node reflects the degree of citation an author has received, where the larger nodes indicate a greater intensity of co citation for that author. In figure 3, nodes for “de massis a.”, “Chrisman j.j.”, “chua j.h.” and “miller d.” appears to be large indicating the aspect that their work is highly co cited. Links between the nodes represents co citation between the authors. The thickness of the links signifies the intensity of co citation between two authors. That means, the thicker the links are the greater number of times those two authors have co cited together.

In the figure 3, “de massis, alfredo” appears to be large, central node in the red cluster, which indicates the significant influence and co citation with other authors with 29 publication and total citation of 2567. Their work is majorly associated with “Family business succession”, “innovation”, entrepreneurial orientation” and “sustainability in family business context”. Another prominent author appears in the figure 3 are “Chrisman j.j.” and “Chua j.h.”. They appear in blue and green clusters respectively and appear to be strongly connected with themes like “Interpersonal dynamics”, “socioemotional wealth”. Further, the works of “miller, danny” and “Nordqvist, mattias” are also notable in the figure 3 with green and red clusters respectively. Their works are in the theme of “governance”, “CSR”, “Ethics”. “Kotlar, Josip” appears to be another author which has its prominent work linked with "de massis a." and "chrisman j.j.", in the themes of “Succession planning in family business” etc.

Figure 3: Co citation analysis

Table 5: Thematic Cluster

Themes identified	Paper Title	Authors	Year	Citations
Family Goals	Reflections on family firm goals and the assessment of performance	Chua J.H., Chrisman J.J., De Massis A., Wang H.	2018	110
	“Where do you want to take your family firm?” A goal hierarchy perspective of family firm internationalization	Basco R.	2017	108
	The Heterogeneity of Family Firms in CSR Engagement: The Role of Values and Stewardship	Marques P., Presas P., Simon A.	2014	214
	Corporate social responsibility in family firms: Status and future directions of a fragmented field	Mariani M.M., Al-Sultan K., De Massis A.	2023	112
	To Merge, Sell, or Liquidate? Socioemotional Wealth, Identity, and Family Business Exit Strategies	Chirico F., Gómez-Mejia L.R., Hellerstedt K., Withers M.	2020	141
	Sustainability in tourism as an innovation driver: An analysis of family firms	Elmo G.C., Arcese G., Valeri M., Poponi S., Pacchera F.	2020	107
	Sustainability as a driver for value creation: A qualitative comparative analysis	Broccardo L., Zicari A.	2020	117
	Family businesses under COVID-19: Inspiring models for facing the crisis	Le Breton-Miller I., Miller D.	2022	56
Succession planning	Family firms in the global economy: Toward a deeper understanding of internationalization determinants	De Massis A., Frattini F., Majocchi A., Piscitello L.	2018	326
	When does transitioning from family to professional management improve firm performance?	Chang S.-J., Shim J.	2015	160
	Family control and family firm valuation by family CEOs: The importance of intergenerational family involvement	Zellweger T.M., Kellermanns F.W., Chrisman J.J., Chua J.H.	2012	653
	The pursuit of international opportunities in family firms: Generational differences	Fang H., Kotlar J., Memili E., Chrisman J.J., De Massis A.	2018	133

	and the role of knowledge-based resources			
	Unlocking innovation potential: A typology of family business innovation postures and the critical role of the family system	Rondi E., De Massis A., Kotlar J.	2019	169
Family Culture	The Heterogeneity of Family Firms in CSR Engagement: The Role of Values and Stewardship	Marques P., Presas P., Simon A.	2014	214
	Managing the Tradition and Innovation Paradox in Family Firms: A Configurational Approach	Erdogan I., Rondi E., De Massis A.	2020	252
	Women's involvement in family firms: Progress and challenges	Campopiano G., De Massis A., Rinaldi F.R., Sciascia S.	2017	159
	Women leaders and firm performance in family business: Evidence from India	Chadwick I.C., Dawson A.	2018	113
	To Merge, Sell, or Liquidate? Socioemotional Wealth, Identity, and Family Business Exit Strategies	Chirico F., Gómez-Mejia L.R., Hellerstedt K., Withers M.	2020	141
	What Do We Know About Business Families? Setting the Stage for Leveraging Family Business Research Through Business Family Lenses	Combs J.G., Shanine K.K., Burrows S., Allen J.A.	2020	97
	Trust and reputation in family businesses: A systematic literature review	Chaudhary S., Dhir A., Ferraris A., Bertoldi B.	2021	111
Entrepreneurial Orientation	Managing the Tradition and Innovation Paradox in Family Firms: A Configurational Approach	Erdogan I., Rondi E., De Massis A.	2020	252
	Kinship and business: how entrepreneurial households facilitate business development	Alsos G.A., Carter S., Ljunggren E.	2014	140
	Unlocking innovation potential: A typology of family business innovation postures and the critical role of the family system	Rondi E., De Massis A., Kotlar J.	2019	169

When does transitioning from family to professional management improve firm performance?	Chang S.-J., Shim J.	2015	160
Family ownership and acquisition behavior in publicly-traded companies	Miller D., Breton-Miller I.L., Lester R.H.	2010	320
Sustainability as a driver for value creation: A qualitative comparative analysis	Broccardo L., Zicari A.	2020	117
Women leaders and firm performance in family business: Evidence from India	Chadwick I.C., Dawson A.	2018	113
Family Business Growth Around the World	Miroshnychenko I., De Massis A., Miller D., Barontini R.	2021	135
Clarifying the strategic advantage of familiness: Unbundling its dimensions and highlighting its paradoxes	Irava W.J., Moores K.	2010	96
Sustainability in tourism as an innovation driver: An analysis of family firms	Elmo G.C., Arcese G., Valeri M., Poponi S., Pacchera F.	2020	107
Family businesses under COVID-19: Inspiring models for facing the crisis	Le Breton-Miller I., Miller D.	2022	56

5.7 Thematic Clustering

In order to understand more, the nature of work done in the said field, we adopted the method of thematic clustering based on bibliography coupling. Bibliography coupling is different from the co citation analysis in the sense that, co citation analysis focuses on seminal work which are highly cited in a particular field of research / domain (Donthu et al., 2021), whereas bibliometric coupling is based on the assumption that if two publication shares the common references, then they are also similar in their content / theme (Kessler, 1963). Bibliographic coupling focusses concentrating publication on the basis of thematic cluster which is ultimately based on shared references (Zupic & ˇCater, 2015). Also, bibliometric coupling focuses on more recent works which may not have gained that much references and hence is sometimes overlooked by co citation analysis (Donthu et al., 2021). Thus, we performed the thematic clustering through bibliographic coupling to understand the theme in our area of research. It will also help us in identifying the independent variables which are responsible for sustainability of family owned small, medium and micro enterprises. Details of the four themes identified is given in table 5 above.

Thematic cluster 1 consisted of articles which can be grouped together into a theme called “Family goals”. This cluster primarily (but not all) focusses on that non financial objective that binds and motivates a family firm which can be a suitable point for a family business to get distinguished from non family business. Goals such as socio emotional wealth (SEW), family identity etc are those points which

significantly influence crucial and strategic decision of family controlled MSMEs. Key influential articles under this theme were one from Chua et al. (2018) with 110 citations. This paper is important and pivotal from the aspect that it explained how unique family firms are and it further explored that how important for a family firm is the non financial goals while taking the strategic decision to move the firm forward. While Marques et al. (2014) in this work "The Heterogeneity of Family Firms in CSR Engagement: The Role of Values and Stewardship" with 214 citations highlighted that how family values in family firms significantly shapes its engagement with society through corporate social responsibility. Chirico et al. (2020) with 141 citations emphasised the role of socioemotional wealth and family values in coming to strategic and crucial business decision. Other notable work in this theme was from Basco (2017) (108 citations), Broccardo & Zicari (2020) (117 citations) and Elmo et al. (2020) (107 citations) which linked sustainability with family values and socioemotional wealth for family firms.

Cluster 2 has papers clubbed into the theme of Succession Planning. This cluster has taken into account the aspects of leadership and its implication on ownership transfer within family controlled MSMEs across generations. It has considered and included all strategic considerations, challenges and other relevant factors which are responsible for smooth transition of ownership from one generation to another. Key contributors to this theme are the one from Zellweger et al. (2012) with 653 citations. It has taken socioemotional wealth perspective into the process of succession planning. It argued that valuation of a family firm moves beyond the financial aspect and also encompasses the desire of previous generation to pass on the control to next generation making it almost necessary for smooth transition across the generation. Another contribution in this cluster of succession planning comes from De Massis et al. (2018) through their work "Family firms in the global economy: Toward a deeper understanding of internationalization determinants" with 326 citations. This paper has taken need for internationalisation for family-owned firms. It has highlighted the factors which are responsible for successful succession planning. One of the important factor it has discussed is the degree of family involvement and its implications cross generational aspirations and successful succession planning. Rondi et al. (2019) in their work "Unlocking innovation potential: A typology of family business innovation postures and the critical role of the family system" with 169 citations has explored the importance and presence of innovation within the family-owned business and how does it effect the cross generational succession.

Cluster 3 has theme of Family Culture. This cluster investigates the implication of various elements of family values like shared values, shared beliefs, shared norms which are very unique to every family and hence forms the important and inseparable part of family values. This cluster further explores the impact of other cultural aspect into factors like innovation, stakeholder relationship and also gender issues. Under this cluster key influential article includes the one from Marques et al. (2014) with their 214 citations. As discussed before, this paper has emphasised the role of family values and culture for the sustainability of family firm. Another work from Erdogan et al. (2020) which has 252 citations has examined how family culture effects the crucial relation between preserving tradition and innovation, a common issue in family-owned firms that impacts their long-term sustainability. The work from Campopiano et al. (2017) with 159 citations and from Chadwick & Dawson (2018) with 113 citations,

highlighted the gender issue within family culture and hence family-owned business and its implications on firm's leadership and its performance, which are particularly relevant for Indian family businesses. Cluster 4 has entrepreneurial orientation as a theme for this cluster. This cluster has taken into consideration the impact of important factors like innovation, proactiveness and risk-taking behaviour etc as an important element in the sustainability of family-owned firm. Some of the influential work in this cluster are from Erdogan et al. (2020) with 252 citations. This paper also has emphasised the importance of innovation and management style in sustainability of the family-owned firm. Another important work from Miller et al. (2010) with 320 citations has emphasised how family ownership influences risk-taking behaviour, specifically in important strategic decisions thereby highlighting an important element for entrepreneurial orientation in family firms. In their work Rondi et al. (2019) "Unlocking innovation potential: A typology of family business innovation postures and the critical role of the family system" with 169 citations emphasised the innovation as an important element for entrepreneurship orientation for the sustainability of family-owned firms.

6. Findings and analysis

The above analysis resulted one conclusion that there is growing interest amongst the scholars about the area of family-owned business. We have seen that there is surge in research activity in this field of research especially after the year 2015 where it got its peak in the year 2023. The analysis revealed that author Alfredo De Massis is the most impactful author and the journal, Journal of Family Business Strategy is the most impactful journal as it is the most cited journal. If we look country wise, The United Kingdom emerged as the leading country in terms of both citations and publications. As far as the India's contribution to this field of research is concern it remains relatively smaller in spite of the fact that in the country's GDP and growth family-owned business plays a very important and crucial role.

Though co-occurrence analysis identified key and important research theme / areas like "family business" with special focus on performance and socioemotional wealth, "entrepreneurship" which is focussing on corporate social responsibility, and also "qualitative research" with emphasis on key methodological approaches. Also, important themes like the one related to "resilience" during crises and "ethics" within family firms were also identified.

But more specifically for the Indian context, thematic clustering based on bibliographic coupling identified four key themes contributing to the sustainability of family-owned MSMEs. These themes identified were:

- i. *Family Goals*: With special emphasis on financial and social goals, this thematic cluster targeted the socioemotional wealth underlying the family-owned business.
- ii. *Succession Planning*: It highlighted the importance of business objective by giving due consideration/ importance to the concept of leadership and ownership transfer across generations, thereby delivering the strategic considerations for smooth transitions.
- iii. *Family Culture*: It investigated the importance of family values, beliefs, culture and norms on sustainability of family-owned business. It further also tried to raise the importance of gender issues within the family.

- iv. *Entrepreneurial Orientation*: With this cluster the focus identified was on management style, corporate governance and ownership style for sustainability of family-owned business.

Thus, these thematic cluster unearthed the factors responsible for the sustainability of family-owned business which is a step forward with the conventional factors.

7. Scope for Further Research

Based on the work done and objective stated in the paper above, the following areas were identified as the area for further research.

- i. There is need to deepen the understanding of the factors responsible for the sustainability of family-owned business. Though the bibliometric analysis identified the four key thematic areas which is responsible for sustainability of family-owned business, there is need to further explore the areas identified. Researcher can also employ qualitative techniques, such as in-depth case studies or interviews, to understand further the thematic cluster so identified. This would in turn would provide more better insights into the reason, that how these factors contribute to the sustainability of family-owned business in India.
- ii. There is greater need to empirically validate the clusters identified in the above work so that it can be used to construct the scale which at the end can be used by future researcher to measure the themes quantifiably.
- iii. There are certain factors which didn't found the place in thematic clustering, yet they are important as far as their effect on the sustainability of family-owned business is concerned. These factors are like government polices, technological advancement, effects of economic policies etc. Future researcher can employ these factors for the further studies for their impact /effect in the sustainability of family-owned business.
- iv. There are certain other important issues identified in this paper like financial and technological limitations, human resource issues, regulatory and compliances issues. Future research can be can be carried out to ascertain the ways to overcome these challenges so that sustainability can be guaranteed.

8. Conclusion

The finding of the above research, which is based on co-occurrence analysis and bibliographic coupling analysis, was in the form of proving several important and key factors responsible for sustainability of family controlled MSMEs. The factors identified included family goals, which was had several key sub factors like socio emotional wealth, family identity etc. which are important and crucial in making the key decisions. Succession planning is another crucial factor identified which involves the leadership transition over the generations with special emphasis on the socio emotional wealth and innovation in the process. There was another factor identified was the strong family culture, which is characterised by shared values, beliefs, norms and its impact on innovation, relation with stakeholders and addressing the important and crucial "gender issues" within the family-owned firms. Finally, another crucial and important factor identified is entrepreneurship orientation which in turn includes innovation,

proactiveness and most importantly risk-taking behaviour for the long-term sustainability of family-owned firms.

The co-occurrence analysis further identified another group of thematic clusters focussed on firms' performance, CSR, internal relational dynamics like ethics, trust, and conflict which all at the end contribute to the firm's sustainability.

Even though there are factors identified by the analysis above, still there are other factors which responsible for sustainability of family controlled Indian MSMEs like limited access to finance, low adoption of technological skills, lower awareness with regard to digital skills, a number of skill gaps and last but important, a complex regulatory compliances/environment.

For the future researcher, there is need to develop the strategies which can help family controlled MSMEs to overcome these challenges which effects greatly the sustainability of these firms. Also, looking at the importance of MSMEs to Indian context, succession planning needs the further research and attention. A close understanding of the complex interconnection between the external industrial, political environment etc and internal family dynamics will also be crucial for developing successful sustainability strategies. Thus, this comprehensive review serves as a clear and basic roadmap thereby guiding researchers and practitioners for developing the strategies for sustainability of family-owned MSMEs in India.

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